

Shifts in distribution and occurrence of grapevine pests under future climate scenarios in Austria

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Abstract

Rising temperatures pose significant challenges for vineyard management, including increased risk from thermophilic insect pests that thrive under warmer conditions. Higher temperatures can drive larger populations, more generations per season, and earlier seasonal activity. This study provides a national-scale assessment by integrating species-specific occurrence models with Huglin Index–based suitability in the GIS-based Agricultural Risk Information System (ARIS). Beyond the state of the art, we demonstrate the first operational, Austria-wide coupling that jointly accounts for temperature and precipitation and covers both current and climatically emerging vineyard areas under present and future scenarios. The investigated pests are projected to occur earlier in the season: the first flight of *Lobesia botrana* advances by up to 12 days by late century under RCP8.5, with minimal regional differences within the ensemble. For *Eupoecilia ambiguella*, advances are smaller yet notable, reaching up to 5 days earlier by late century under RCP8.5. For *Scaphoideus titanus*, earlier first occurrences are expected, with up to 14 days earlier for the first nymphal stage and up to 10 days for the third nymphal stage by late century under RCP8.5. These shifts align with broadly uniform temperature increases across Austria and pronounced regional variability in precipitation, underscoring the need to consider both drivers. The applied prediction models emphasized temperature while incorporating precipitation to capture additional environmental influences. Collectively, the findings support earlier, better-targeted interventions and inform climate-resilient viticulture planning, highlighting the value of integrating climate scenarios into pest risk management and maintaining continued research and monitoring.

32 **Keyword:** *Lobesia botrana*, *Eupoecilia ambiguella*, *Scaphoideus titanus*, Huglin Index, prediction
33 models, Agricultural Risk Information System (ARIS), viticulture adaptation

34

35 **1. Introduction**

36 Viticulture is among the agricultural sectors most exposed to climate change because grapevines are
37 highly sensitive to local thermal and hydric conditions (Jones and Webb 2010; van Leeuwen and Darriet
38 2016; van Leeuwen et al. 2004; Micciché et al. 2025). Rising temperatures, shifting precipitation
39 patterns, and an increase in extreme weather events, such as hailstorms, late frosts, and heatwaves,
40 are already affecting grapevine growth and wine production (Comte et al. 2024; Kovács et al. 2018).
41 Beyond these direct effects, climate change can also disrupt vineyard food webs by altering trophic
42 interactions among pests, their natural enemies, and other organisms (Reineke and Thiéry 2016;
43 Castex et al. 2018). Warming is expected to favour thermophilic species, exacerbating risks for
44 viticulture (Santos et al. 2020).

45 Insect pests, such as the European grape berry moth (*Eupoecilia ambiguella*) (Hübner), the European
46 grapevine moth (*Lobesia botrana*) (Denis and Schiffermüller) (Lepidoptera: Tortricidae), and the
47 American grapevine leafhopper (*Scaphoideus titanus*) (Ball) (Hemiptera: Cicadellidae), pose a serious
48 threat to grape production in Austria. While *E. ambiguella* and *L. botrana* larvae cause damage by
49 feeding on both flowers and berries, which can lead to secondary fungal infections (Hoppmann and
50 Holst 1989; Fermaud and Le Menn 1989), *S. titanus* causes damage by transmitting the destructive
51 Grapevine flavescence dorée phytoplasma (FDp) from vine to vine (EFSA 2014; Gonella et al. 2024).
52 FDp reduces grape quality, vine vitality and yield, often leading to the death of infected grapevines
53 (Caudwell 1990; Morone et al. 2007; EFSA et al. 2016).

54 Climate warming is expected to intensify these risks by accelerating pest development, increasing
55 survival and voltinism, advancing phenology, and expanding pest ranges to higher elevations and
56 latitudes (Altermatt 2010; Yan et al. 2017; Tosato et al. 2023). A longer and warmer growing season
57 could amplify pest activity, leading to greater crop damage and production losses (Lastuvka 2009;
58 Gutierrez and Ponti 2014; Bradshaw et al. 2016; Paini et al. 2016). Rising temperatures and altered
59 seasonal weather patterns are likely to shift pest distributions, for example, to higher altitudes,
60 promote the development of additional generations, advance the timing of pest occurrence, and
61 increase the prevalence of insect-transmitted plant diseases (Martín-Vertedor et al. 2010; Pavan et al.
62 2013; Reis et al. 2022). Together, these changes will heighten the challenges faced by vineyard
63 management (Comte et al. 2024; Svobodova et al. 2014; Castex et al. 2018; Castex et al. 2023;
64 Gutierrez et al. 2018; Skendžić et al. 2021; Ricciardi et al. 2024).

65 In Austria, *L. botrana* and *E. ambiguella* typically produce two generations per year, but a third
66 generation has occasionally been observed under favourable conditions (Polesny et al. 2000; Bauer et
67 al. 2017; Höbaus 1988). However, if temperatures rise excessively, *L. botrana* may experience reduced
68 lifespan and reproductive success, which could limit its population growth (Iltis et al. 2020). Similarly,
69 climate warming could enable *S. titanus* to produce a second generation, while expanding its
70 distribution upslope and northward. Rising temperatures are also expected to accelerate the timing of
71 *S. titanus* occurrences and increase the number of eggs laid, further exacerbating its impact on
72 vineyards (Sneiders et al. 2019; Comte et al. 2024).

73 Accurate prediction of pest activity is essential to mitigating the risk of damage and ensuring effective
74 pest management. Degree-day (temperature-sum) models, which accumulate heat above species-
75 specific base temperatures, are widely applied for phenology forecasting, but discrepancies between
76 model predictions and actual pest occurrences highlight the need for more refined models that
77 incorporate additional weather variables (e.g., humidity, precipitation, solar radiation) and potentially
78 nonlinear responses (Blümel et al. 2020; Kolkmann 2021).

79 Addressing these challenges, this study has three primary objectives: (i) To develop and evaluate
80 prediction models for pest occurrence by integrating long-term monitoring data with different weather
81 variables; (ii) to assess and map future shifts in climatologically suitable wine-growing regions under
82 climate scenarios in context to grapevine pest occurrence; and (iii) to project shifts in the timing of the
83 first seasonal occurrence, including the first and second flights of *E. ambiguella* and *L. botrana* and the
84 first and third nymphal stages of *S. titanus*, under projected climates, with emphasis on earlier seasonal
85 activity. The findings provide critical insights into the long-term consequences of climate change on
86 pest populations, spatial shifts of suitable vineyard production conditions and related pest
87 occurrences, support sustainable pest management strategies, and help strengthen the resilience of
88 Austrian vineyards in the face of a changing climate.

89

90 **2. Data and methodology**

91 **2.1 The ARIS model**

92 The Agricultural Risk Information System (ARIS) is a GIS-based modelling system designed to assess and
93 manage weather-related abiotic and biotic risks, as well as crop management and growing conditions
94 in Austria (Eitzinger et al. 2024). It supports a range of applications, including forecasts, weather
95 observations and climate change projections. Operating on a daily basis, ARIS utilizes a spatial grid of
96 1 km for weather data, while soil conditions are modelled at a finer resolution of 0.5 km, based on the
97 Austrian soil map. The system's indicators primarily focus on general cropping conditions or risks

98 derived from daily weather variables, which can be supplemented with soil moisture data. However, it
99 does not account for other non-weather-related limitations (Eitzinger et al. 2024).
100 In addition to general indicators, ARIS includes crop-specific risk indicators based on algorithms that
101 simulate the phenological development of five major crops. These indicators emphasize the soil-crop
102 water balance and the combined effects of drought and heat stress. Furthermore, biotic indicators are
103 integrated to assess risks from pests and diseases that are significant for Austrian agricultural
104 conditions. To assess potential shifts in Austrian wine growing areas under different climate change
105 scenarios, we used the Huglin Index (HI), a measure of growing season warmth that combines daily
106 mean and maximum temperatures with a latitude correction. The ARIS model included newly
107 developed algorithms, in accordance with the generated prediction models, for the first occurrence of
108 the first and second flights of *L. botrana* and *E. ambiguella*, as well as the first and third nymphal stages
109 (N1 and N3) of *S. titanus*. Simulations were conducted across all arable land in Austria (Eitzinger et al.,
110 2024).

111

112 **2.2 Austrian climate change projections - ÖKS15**

113 The Austrian climate scenarios dataset, ÖKS15, was developed to provide a standardized basis for
114 climate impact studies and risk analyses in Austria (Chimani et al. 2016). This dataset offers climate
115 change data for the 20th and 21st centuries in a probabilistic framework, based on long-term, high-
116 quality, and high-resolution gridded observational data (1 x 1 km grid spacing, daily resolution). It
117 includes an analysis of historical climate changes as well as bias-corrected regional climate projections
118 for Austria (Chimani et al. 2016; Chimani et al. 2019).

119 The historical analysis utilized the SPARTACUS (Spatiotemporal Reanalysis Dataset for Climate in
120 Austria) datasets for both temperature and precipitation at 1 × 1 km daily resolution as the
121 observational reference for bias correction and validation (Hiebl and Frei 2016; Chimani et al. 2020).
122 The climate projections were based on Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs) (van Vuuren et
123 al. 2011; Moss et al. 2010; Clarke et al. 2007; Riahi et al. 2007) and the latest available EURO-CORDEX
124 Regional Climate Model (RCM) ensemble (Jacob et al. 2014). A total of thirteen climate projections
125 were generated by combining six regional models with five General Circulation Models (GCMs). These
126 projections, with a horizontal resolution of 12.5 km, were developed for two RCP scenarios: RCP4.5
127 (moderate development) and RCP8.5 (high-emissions), covering the period 1971–2100. The RCM data
128 from the EURO-CORDEX initiative (12.5 km grid size) were interpolated onto the SPARTACUS grid of
129 observational data (1 km grid size). Biases for each RCM were corrected using Scaled Distribution

130 Mapping (SDM) (Switanek et al. 2017), performed on a grid-cell-by-grid cell basis without considering
131 potential spatial correlations (Chimani et al. 2019; Chimani et al. 2020).

132 For this study, five different Austrian climate projections were selected, each based on two emission
133 scenarios (RCP4.5 and RCP8.5) resulting in a total of ten projections. To sample model spread, the five
134 members were chosen based on availability and diversity in driving GCMs/RCMs (Table 1). The
135 reference period was defined as 2003-2022, corresponding to the 20 years for which INCA (Integrated
136 Nowcasting through Comprehensive Analysis) grid-based weather data (Haiden et al. 2010; Haiden et
137 al. 2012) were available. These data served as input to the ARIS model. It should be noted that this
138 period is already strongly influenced by climate change relative to historical baselines. In Austria, the
139 mean air temperature has increased by 1.1-1.8 °C from the 1961–1990 to 1991–2020 periods. This
140 warming trend is reflected in a substantial shift in climate indices: on average, Austria now experiences
141 16.7 fewer frost days and 7.5 more hot days than in the mid-20th century. Furthermore, while the
142 number of days with light precipitation (daily total ≥ 1 mm) has decreased, more intense precipitation
143 events (daily total ≥ 10 mm) have become more frequent (Tilg and Chimani 2025; Peßenteiner et al.
144 2021).

145 The periods 2021-2050 (mean 2035) and 2071-2100 (mean 2085) were chosen to represent the near
146 future and the end of the century, respectively. The seasonal differences in temperature (T [K]) and
147 precipitation (P [mm]) between each future period and the reference (2003-2022), for the individual
148 ÖKS15 projections and the ensemble mean under RCP4.5 and RCP8.5, are summarised in Table 1. Note
149 that the 2003–2022 reference period falls outside the historical reference period (1971–2000) used in
150 the original bias correction of the ÖKS15 dataset (Peßenteiner et al. 2021).

151 Moreover, observed warming since the 1980s exceeds the near-term warming projected by ÖKS15.
152 This underestimation likely reflects a combination of underestimated greenhouse-gas impacts in the
153 driving climate models and the historical cooling effect of air pollution masking true warming. These
154 factors should be considered when interpreting the results and may render even RCP8.5 a conservative
155 projection for some indicators (Formayer et al. 2025).

156
157 *Figure 1: Mean temperature bias (ΔT_{mean}) of selected ÖKS15 projections vs. INCA reference (7.04°C, 2003–2022).*

158
159 The ÖKS15 projections show a mean bias of 0.14°C against the INCA reference (7.04°C) for 2003–2022,
160 with RCP4.5 models averaging 0.11°C cooler and RCP8.5 models 0.15°C warmer. CM5A-MR IPSL-INERIS-
161 WRF under RCP8.5 exhibits the largest positive bias (+0.90°C), while EC-EARTH DMI-HIRHAM5 under
162 RCP8.5 is coolest (-0.27°C) (Figure 1). To avoid conflating dataset-specific offsets with climate-change
163 signals, all change estimates were therefore computed as within-model anomalies (future 2021-
164 2050/2071-2100 minus 2003–2022). Uncertainty is summarised by the inter-member range; ensemble
165 means are also provided.

166
167 *Table 1: Seasonal and annual differences in temperature (T) [K] and precipitation (P) [mm] for the selected ÖKS15*
168 *projections and ensemble means (RCP4.5 and RCP8.5): 2021-2050 (2035) vs. 2003-2022 and 2071-2100 (2085)*
169 *vs. 2003-2022.*

ÖKS 15 projection	Time	Spring		Summer		Autumn		Winter		Year	
RCP4.5											
		T[K]	P[mm]	T[K]	P[mm]	T[K]	P[mm]	T[K]	P[mm]	T[K]	P[mm]
CNRM-CM5 CLMcom-CCLM4	2035	-0.2	-17	0.3	-10.3	0.0	1.8	-0.1	3.3	0.0	-22.4
	2085	0.8	-7.3	1.2	-3.9	1.1	8.4	1.5	8.5	1.2	5.7
CNRM-CM5 CNRM-ALADIN53	2035	0.1	-21	0.2	25.3	0.1	3.7	0.2	8.1	0.1	15.9
	2085	1.5	2.2	1.4	44.5	1.4	27.5	1.5	13.2	1.5	87.5
EC-EARTH DMI-HIRHAM5	2035	0.7	2.4	0.7	-6.9	0.6	-3.3	0.2	8.8	0.6	1.0
	2085	1.3	23.4	1.2	28.6	0.9	36.2	0.9	29.5	1.1	117.8
CM5A-MR IPSL-INERIS-WRF	2035	0.3	18.8	0.5	1.2	0.5	-6.7	0.6	-16	0.5	-2.5
	2085	1.5	25.3	0.8	64.6	1.6	5.2	1.9	-4.9	1.4	90.2
MPI-ESM-LR-CCLM4	2035	0.3	18.2	0.8	2.5	0.6	2.7	0.7	10.1	0.6	33.6
	2085	1.1	0.5	1.5	-21.4	1.2	2.3	1.5	18.1	1.3	-0.5
Ensemble mean	2035	0.2	0.2	0.5	2.4	0.4	-0.4	0.3	2.9	0.4	5.1
	2085	1.2	8.8	1.2	22.5	1.3	15.9	1.4	12.9	1.3	60.2
RCP8.5											
		T[K]	P[mm]	T[K]	P[mm]	T[K]	P[mm]	T[K]	P[mm]	T[K]	P[mm]
CNRM-CM5 CLMcom-CCLM4	2035	0.5	-18.2	0.6	-3.9	0.6	32.2	0.4	15.8	0.5	25.9
	2085	2.2	2.6	2.7	-12.8	2.9	30.8	3.4	29.2	2.8	49.9
CNRM-CM5 CNRM-ALADIN53	2035	0.9	-0.1	0.5	19.9	0.9	53.2	0.5	31.8	0.7	105
	2085	3.3	30.6	3.6	36.0	3.4	44.0	3.0	29.6	3.3	140.3
EC-EARTH DMI-HIRHAM5	2035	0.7	10.5	0.9	-18.5	0.9	27.5	0.4	16.1	0.7	60.9
	2085	2.3	26.6	3.2	9.5	2.8	26.5	2.6	46.5	2.7	109.3
CM5A-MR IPSL-INERIS-WRF	2035	-0.4	10.2	-0.7	50.9	0.3	18.7	0.1	18.5	-0.2	98.4
	2085	2.3	9.0	1.4	133.4	2.5	54.3	3.8	17.8	2.5	214.7

MPI-ESM-LR-CCLM4	2035	0.5	-2.4	0.5	20.8	0.3	14.5	0.3	17.8	0.4	50.8
	2085	2.2	9.7	2.9	-44.9	2.8	14.2	3.4	53.4	2.8	32.5
Ensemble mean	2035	0.4	-0.5	0.4	12.6	0.6	29	0.3	19.8	0.4	60.9
	2085	2.5	15.7	2.7	24.2	2.9	33.9	3.2	35.6	2.8	109.3

170

171 2.3 Monitoring data

172 For *S. titanus* the monitoring data was derived from 16 monitoring sites in six different wine-growing
173 regions of Austria over several consecutive years (2013-2022). The monitoring sites were merged into
174 seven site clusters according to their vicinity to GeoSphere Austria reference weather stations
175 (Kolkmann et al. 2025a). Monitoring was carried out weekly to determine when the different nymphal
176 stages first appear in the season and to record the number of individuals present. At each site, 400
177 random leaves (10 leaves per vine, 10 vines per row and four rows per site) were visually examined.
178 The 1st nymphal stage was identified with a magnifying glass and the 2nd and 3rd nymphal stages were
179 determined using a field microscope. The occurrence of N1 marks the start of *S. titanus* monitoring,
180 while N3 marks the start of control measures, as phytoplasma transmission can be prevented at this
181 stage (Falzoi et al. 2014). For both N1 and N3, 46 datasets were available.

182 The monitoring data from *L. botrana* and *E. ambiguella* were derived from four decades (1980-2022)
183 of consecutive observations by the Austrian forecasting services at 60 monitoring sites. The monitoring
184 sites were located in 14 different wine-growing regions and were merged into 14 site clusters
185 (Kolkmann et al. 2025b). Monitoring was carried out in 1 to 3 days intervals and the adults of both
186 grape moth species were monitored either with pheromone traps or with the branch cage method.
187 The branch cage method enabled the observation of various developmental stages of *L. botrana* and
188 *E. ambiguella* under real-time field conditions (Polesny et al. 2000). For the 1st/2nd flight, a total of
189 224 datasets for *L. botrana* and 203 datasets for *E. ambiguella* were available (Kolkmann et al. 2025b).
190 The daily measured weather data from nine weather parameters were provided by GeoSphere Austria
191 (<https://data.hub.geosphere.at/>) for the seven reference weather stations, which were closest to the
192 monitoring site clusters of *S. titanus* and for the 14 reference weather stations, closest to the
193 monitoring site clusters of *L. botrana* and *E. ambiguella*. For the multiple linear regression (MLR)
194 analysis, the weather parameters were processed into different weather variables (Kolkmann et al.
195 2025a; Kolkmann et al. 2025b). Occasionally occurring data gaps were either filled with additional
196 weather data from nearby weather stations or with SPARTACUS grid datasets. For the air temperature,
197 an altitude correction was applied if the sea level difference between the monitoring site and the
198 respective reference weather station exceeded 100 m (decrease of 0.6 °C for each 100 m increase of
199 sea level).

200

201 **2.4 Data compilation**

202 Pest models were developed using MLR analysis, conducted with IBM® SPSS® Statistics (Version 26).
203 The model developing consisted of two main steps, which are a calibration step (generation of the
204 model) and validation step (testing of the calibrated model). The MLR models for predicting
205 *L. botrana*/*E. ambiguella* 1st/2nd flight were developed in a previous study, which also describes the
206 underlying calibration and validation procedure (Kolkmann et al. 2025b).

207 For *S. titanus* N1 / N3 preexisting MLR models (Kolkmann et al. 2025a) were adapted and validated
208 using statistical indicators such as RMSE, R² and BIAS.

209 In the ARIS model, the Huglin Index was applied to determine potential wine-growing areas under
210 current conditions and different climate change scenarios. This bioclimatic index evaluates a region's
211 suitability for viticulture by calculating cumulative temperatures during the growing season (April 1 to
212 September 30) (Huglin and Schneider 1998).

213 Additionally, the timing of the first occurrence of *L. botrana*, *E. ambiguella* (1st and 2nd flight), and
214 *S. titanus* (1st and 3rd nymphal stages) was specifically calculated for Austria's wine-growing regions
215 across different time periods. Results were visualized through maps, and 21 specific locations
216 representing different climate zones were selected for detailed analysis (Figure 2).

217
218 *Figure 2. Huglin Index (mean 2003-2022) and selected sites for evaluation.*

219
220 The individual climate change projections and their deviations for the 2nd flight of *L. botrana* and
221 *E. ambiguella* were analysed for four important wine-growing regions in Austria (Langenlois,

222 Lutzmannsburg, Stammersdorf, and Retz) as well as for Zwettl, a site characterized by a cool temperate
 223 continental climate without viticulture (Figure 2).

224

225 3. Results

226 3.1 Calibration and validation of the pest models

227 The MLR models predicting the 1st/2nd flight of *L. botrana* and *E. ambiguella* consisted of one variable
 228 processed from the weather parameter mean temperature and one from precipitation. The MLR model
 229 predicting the 2nd flight of *E. ambiguella* furthermore included a weather variable processed from
 230 global radiation (Kolkmann et al. 2025b).

231 For *S. titanus* N1 / N3 preexisting MLR models (Kolkmann et al. 2025a) were adapted and validated.
 232 The MLR models for *S. titanus* included weather variables based on the weather parameters
 233 (maximum/mean) temperature and precipitation. The variance inflation factor (VIF) displayed low
 234 linear (< 4) connection between the input variables of each *S. titanus* MLR model (O'Brien 2007). All
 235 independent variables (= weather variables) were statistically significant ($P < 0.05$) (Table 2).

236

237 *Table 2. Results of stepwise multiple linear regression analysis predicting the day of year of first seasonal*
 238 *occurrence of the 1st and 3rd nymphal stage of S. titanus.*

Developmental stage	Model variables	B	SE	β	t	P	VIF
1st nymphal stage	Intercept	262.479	10.807	-	24.288	< 0.001	-
	T _{max}	-6.428	0.584	-1.365	-11.000	< 0.001	2.621
	T _{mean} < 5	-0.348	0.060	-0.702	-5.811	< 0.001	2.480
	Precip _{sum}	-0.020	0.008	-0.199	-2.483	0.018	1.095
Note: R ² _{adj.} = 0.794 (n = 35, P < 0.001).							
3rd nymphal stage	Intercept	202.154	4.680	-	43.197	< 0.001	-
	T _{base} 8.5	-0.065	0.009	-0.775	-6.985	< 0.001	1.008
	Precip _{sum}	-0.049	0.017	0.318	-2.866	0.008	1.008
Note: R ² _{adj.} = 0.634 (n = 30, P < 0.001).							

239 *B = B-coefficient (unstandardised coefficient); SE = standard error of unstandardised coefficient; β = Beta-coefficient (standardised coefficient); t = t-statistic;*

240 *P = significance; VIF = variance inflation factor; R²_{adj.} = adjusted coefficient of determination; n = sample size.*

241

242 The final MLR equations and their applied weekly calculation periods for predicting the first seasonal
 243 occurrence of *S. titanus* N1 / N3 are presented in Table 3.

244

245 *Table 3. Adapted MLR equations and applied weekly calculation period for the prediction of the DOY (= day of*
 246 *year) of first seasonal occurrence of S. titanus N1/N3.*

MLR model for <i>S. titanus</i>	Equation	Weekly calculation period
---------------------------------	----------	---------------------------

1st nymphal stage	$DOY = 262.479 + (T_{max} \times -6.428) + (T_{mean} < 5 \times -0.348) + (Precip_{sum} \times -0.020)$	1 February to 6 June*
3rd nymphal stage	$DOY = 202.154 + (T_{base} 8.5 \times -0.065) + (Precip_{sum} \times -0.049)$	1 May to 18 June

* in leap years: 1 February to 5 June.

247
248

249 The validation of the two *S. titanus* MLR models displayed for N1 high and for N3 very high prediction
250 accuracies (Table 4). The adapted MLR model for predicting *S. titanus* N1 forecasted the first seasonal
251 occurrence on average 2.4 days too late, while the model for N3 predicted it, on average, 0.6 days too
252 early (Table 4). Compared to the preexisting MLR models (Kolkmann et al. 2025a), the adapted MLR
253 models for *S. titanus* N1 and N3 demonstrated improved prediction accuracy.

254

255 *Table 4. Statistical indicators for validating the calibrated MLR models to predict the first seasonal occurrence of*
256 *S. titanus N1/N3.*

Grapevine pest species		<i>n</i> datasets	Statistical indicators		
Pest species	Developmental stage		R ²	RMSE	BIAS
<i>S. titanus</i>	1st nymphal stage	7	0.819	3.392	2.370
	3rd nymphal stage	11	0.773	2.541	-0.619

257

258 The correspondence between the observed and predicted first seasonal occurrence in day of year
259 (DOY) with the validation dataset was high for N1 with a tendency to predict too late and for N3 the
260 correspondence was also high with a tendency to predict the first seasonal occurrence too early (Figure
261 3).

262

263
 264 *Figure 3. Linear regressions between observed and predicted day of year (DOY) to predict the first seasonal*
 265 *occurrence of S. titanus N1 and N3, from 2013 to 2022 (○ = calibration dataset and Δ = validation dataset).*
 266 *Deviations above the 1:1 line indicate a too early forecast, below a too late forecast.*

267
 268 **3.2 Climate change impacts on wine-growing regions and pest dynamics**

269 **3.2.1 Climate change impacts based on Austrian climate projections (ÖKS15)**

270 The changes in temperature and precipitation for 2035 and 2085, compared to the reference period,
 271 are shown as ensemble means (RCP4.5 and RCP8.5) in Figure 3. For Austria, the ensemble indicates
 272 temperature increases of +0.4°C by 2035 and +1.3°C by 2085 under the RCP4.5 scenario, and +0.4°C by
 273 2035 and +2.8°C by 2085 under the RCP8.5 scenario. Precipitation is projected to increase by +5.1 mm
 274 (2035) and +60.2 mm (2085) under RCP4.5, and by +60.9 mm (2035) and +109.3 mm (2085) under
 275 RCP8.5. While temperature increases are relatively uniform across Austria, precipitation changes show
 276 significant regional variability (Figure 4).

277

278

279 *Figure 4. Annual differences in precipitation [mm] and temperature [°C] for 2021–2050 vs. 2003–2022 and*
 280 *2071–2100 vs. 2003–2022 — ensemble mean for RCP4.5 and RCP8.5.*

281

282 Figure 5 summarizes seasonal and annual differences for Austria as dots (ensemble means) with
 283 whiskers indicating minima and maxima between ensemble members for the periods 2021–2050 vs.
 284 2003–2022 and 2071–2100 vs. 2003–2022. For temperature (ΔT [K]), the near-term ensemble means
 285 are small and broadly consistent across seasons, whereas by late century ΔT increases across all

286 seasons, is strongest in summer (JJA), and is larger under RCP8.5 than under RCP4.5. Precipitation (ΔP
 287 [mm]) shows much larger model spread: near term ensemble means are modest and whiskers
 288 frequently straddle zero, indicating low confidence in the sign of change; by late century, annual and
 289 summer means tend to increase, particularly under RCP8.5, but with substantial uncertainty between
 290 ensemble members.

291
 292 *Figure 5. Seasonal and annual temperature and precipitation differences for Austria (ΔT [K], ΔP [mm]). Panels*
 293 *show RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 for 2021–2050 vs. 2003–2022 and 2071–2100 vs. 2003–2022. Dots denote ensemble*
 294 *means across five ÖKS-15 members; whiskers show inter-member minima and maxima.*

295
 296 **3.2.2 Climate change effect on European grapevine moth (*L. botrana*)**

297 Future temperature increases are expected to significantly expand Austria’s wine growing regions, with
 298 the most pronounced changes under RCP8.5. This expansion is defined by areas with a Huglin Index
 299 greater than 1500, as shown in Figure 6. Between 2035 and 2085, rising temperature sums will enable
 300 new areas to meet the thresholds required for viticulture, with the suitable area share projected to
 301 expand by 10% (2035) and 30% (2085) under RCP4.5, and by 7% (2035) and 44% (2085) under RCP8.5.
 302 In eastern Austria, where wine is already cultivated, the changing climate is likely to favour a shift
 303 toward heat resilient grape varieties, reflecting the region’s increasing suitability for warmer
 304 conditions. Overall, this expansion highlights the potential for both new and existing wine growing
 305 areas to adapt to a future changing climate.

306 The ensemble mean for RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 (Figure 6) illustrates the timing of the first flight of *L.*
 307 *botrana* for now (2003–2022), 2035 (2021–2050), and 2085 (2071–2100) as day of year (DOY), with
 308 companion panels showing changes relative to now (days). Currently, the first occurrence is observed
 309 in eastern Austria as early as late April (around DOY 118) and along the Danube up to Upper Austria by

310 mid-May (DOY 130+). In 2035, an earlier occurrence of about one day is expected under RCP4.5,
 311 especially in southern Austria, and 1–2 days under RCP8.5. By the end of the century, advances reach
 312 up to 5 days under RCP4.5 and up to 10 days or more under RCP8.5, with minimal regional differences
 313 within the ensemble. Complementing the maps, boxplots for viticulture-suitable areas (HI ≥ 1500;
 314 Figure 6c) show mean advances in 2021–2050 under RCP4.5 ($\Delta\text{LB} \approx -0.17 \pm 0.17$ days; mean \pm SD across
 315 grid cells with HI ≥ 1500) versus stronger advances under RCP8.5 (-1.73 ± 0.24 days), intensifying by
 316 2071-2100 to -3.45 ± 0.35 days (RCP4.5; 5-95%: -3.94 to -2.77) and -8.70 ± 1.01 days (RCP8.5; 5-95%: $-$
 317 9.84 to -6.62). Negative values indicate earlier first flights.

318 (a)

319

320 (b)

321

322 (c)

323
 324 *Figure 6. First occurrence of the first flight of L. botrana (ensemble mean). Top row: day of year (DOY) for 2003–*
 325 *2022, 2021–2050, and 2071–2100. Bottom row: changes relative to 2003–2022 (days) for 2021–2050 and 2071–*
 326 *2100. Results are shown for (a) RCP4.5 and (b) RCP8.5. The maps are restricted to areas suitable for viticulture,*
 327 *defined as Huglin Index ≥ 1500 . (c) Boxplots of changes in first-flight timing (ΔLB , days) within areas with HI \geq*
 328 *1500; the horizontal line marks no change (0).*

329
 330 Considering the individual selected locations and climate change projections, hardly any changes are
 331 to be expected in the near future (Table 5). The exception is CNRM-CM5_CNRM-ALADIN53 - RCP8.5,
 332 which shows values of up to -5 days. By the end of the century, an earlier occurrence of up to 6 days
 333 can be expected for RCP4.5, while RCP8.5 shows values of up to 14 days. Here too, CNRM-CM5_CNRM-
 334 ALADIN53, followed by CM5A-MR_IPSL-INERIS-WRF and EC-EARTH_DMI-HIRHAM5 have the strongest
 335 effects. The CNRM-CM5_CLMcom-CCLM4 projection shows the lowest values. No regional differences
 336 are apparent in Figure 5a, in contrast to the evident variations in Figure 5b.

337
 338 *Table 5. Differences in the first occurrence of the 1st flight L. botrana between 2035 (2021-2050) and now (2003-*
 339 *2022) as well as 2085 (2071-2100) and now (2003-2022) - in days.*

		CNRM-CM5_CLMcom-CCLM4	CNRM-CM5_CNRM-ALADIN53	EC-EARTH_DMI-HIRHAM5	CM5A-MR_IPSL-INERIS-WRF	MPI-ESM-LR-CCLM4	CNRM-CM5_CLMcom-CCLM4	CNRM-CM5_CNRM-ALADIN53	EC-EARTH_DMI-HIRHAM5	CM5A-MR_IPSL-INERIS-WRF	MPI-ESM-LR-CCLM4
RCP4.5											
Location	Climate and growth zones	2035					2085				
Seckau	Eastern Intermediate Alps - southern part	1	0	-1	1	0	-2	-2	-3	-3	-2
Gumpoldskirchen	Lower Austrian eastern fringe of the Alps	2	1	-1	0	0	-3	-6	-3	-5	-2
Enns	Northern Alpine Foreland - Eastern part	2	0	-1	0	0	-2	-5	-3	-5	-3
Gumpenstein		1	1	-1	0	-1	-3	-2	-3	-5	-3
Hoersching		2	0	-1	0	0	-2	-6	-3	-5	-2
Melk		2	1	-1	0	0	-2	-5	-4	-5	-2
Rum	Northern Intermediate Alps - Western part	1	0	-1	0	-1	-3	-3	-3	-7	-4
Ahrenberg	Pannonian lowlands and hills	2	1	-1	0	0	-2	-5	-4	-5	-2
Andau		1	1	-2	0	0	-3	-5	-4	-6	-2

Berg		1	1	-2	0	0	-3	-5	-4	-6	-2
Langenlois		2	1	-1	0	0	-2	-6	-4	-5	-2
Lutzmannsburg		1	1	-2	0	0	-3	-5	-4	-5	-3
Rutzendorf		2	1	-1	0	0	-3	-5	-4	-6	-2
Schoengrabern		2	1	-1	0	0	-2	-5	-4	-5	-2
Stammersdorf		2	1	-1	0	0	-3	-6	-4	-6	-2
Zwerndorf		2	1	-1	0	0	-3	-5	-3	-6	-2
Oberwoelz	Subcontinental Inner Alps - Eastern part	1	0	-2	1	-1	-3	-2	-3	-3	-3
Ratsch		1	1	-2	0	-1	-2	-5	-4	-4	-3
Wagna Leibnitz	Sub-Illyrian hills and terraces	1	1	-2	0	-1	-2	-5	-4	-5	-4
Gmuend	Waldviertel region	0	0	-2	0	-1	-3	-3	-3	-3	-3
Horn		2	1	-1	0	0	-2	-5	-4	-5	-2
RCP8.5											
Seckau	Eastern Intermediate Alps - southern part	-1	-1	0	-1	-1	-5	-8	-7	-9	-7
Gumpoldskirchen	Lower Austrian eastern fringe of the Alps	-1	-5	1	0	-2	-6	-14	-9	-11	-8
Enns	Northern Alpine Foreland - Eastern part	-1	-5	0	1	-1	-6	-14	-9	-10	-7
Gumpenstein		-1	-2	1	0	-1	-8	-7	-8	-12	-10
Hoersching		-1	-5	0	1	-1	-6	-14	-9	-10	-7
Melk		-1	-5	1	0	-1	-6	-14	-9	-11	-8
Rum	Northern Intermediate Alps - Western part	-1	-4	0	0	-2	-10	-11	-9	-16	-13
Ahrenberg	Pannonian lowlands and hills	-1	-5	1	0	-2	-6	-14	-10	-11	-8
Andau		-1	-4	1	0	-2	-6	-13	-10	-10	-9
Berg		-1	-4	1	-1	-2	-7	-13	-10	-11	-8
Langenlois		-1	-4	1	0	-2	-6	-14	-9	-10	-8
Lutzmannsburg		-1	-4	1	0	-2	-6	-13	-10	-10	-9
Rutzendorf		-1	-4	1	0	-2	-6	-13	-10	-11	-8
Schoengrabern		-1	-4	1	0	-2	-6	-14	-9	-10	-8
Stammersdorf		-1	-5	1	0	-2	-7	-14	-10	-11	-9
Zwerndorf		-1	-4	1	0	-2	-6	-13	-10	-11	-8
Oberwoelz	Subcontinental Inner Alps - Eastern part	-1	-2	0	-1	-2	-7	-8	-8	-11	-9
Ratsch		-1	-4	1	-1	-2	-6	-13	-9	-11	-9
Wagna Leibnitz	Sub-Illyrian hills and terraces	-1	-4	1	-1	-3	-7	-14	-10	-12	-9
Gmuend	Waldviertel region	-1	-2	0	0	-2	-7	-9	-9	-10	-9
Horn		-1	-4	1	0	-2	-6	-14	-9	-10	-7

340

341 The deviations of the individual climate projections as well as ensemble means on the first day of
342 occurrence of *L. botrana* 2nd flight in the selected locations between 2021-2050 vs. 2003-2022 and
343 2075-2100 vs. 2003-2022 are shown in Figure 7. This shows a mean value of -2 days (RCP4.5) and -3
344 days (RCP8.5) in 2035. The five locations examined show the same trend on average. At the end of the
345 century, an earlier occurrence of 7 days for RCP4.5 and 8 to 11 days for RCP8.5 can be expected
346 (ensemble mean). Zwettl, the coldest site, has the smallest shift.

dashed line: ensemble mean

347
 348 *Figure 7. Deviations in the first day of occurrence of Lobesia botrana 2nd flight in Langenlois, Lutzmannsburg,*
 349 *Retz, Stammersdorf, and Zwettl between 2021-2050 vs 2003-2022 and 2071-2100 vs 2003-2022: ensemble*
 350 *mean (black dashed lines) and selected ÖKS15 projections differences (bars).*

351

352 3.2.3 Climate change effect on European grape berry moth (*E. ambiguella*)

353 For *E. ambiguella*, advances are smaller than for *L. botrana*. Under RCP4.5 (ensemble mean), virtually
 354 no change is expected by 2035, aside from about one day earlier in southern Austria (Figure 8a). By
 355 2085, the first flight advances by up to 3 days. Under RCP8.5, an advance of 1–2 days is widespread by
 356 2035, increasing to up to 4 days by 2085 (Figure 8b). Complementing the maps, boxplots restricted to
 357 viticulture-suitable areas ($HI \geq 1500$; Figure 8c) indicate modest near-term shifts under RCP4.5 ($\Delta EA =$
 358 -0.16 ± 0.16 days) and stronger shifts under RCP8.5 ($\Delta EA = -0.41 \pm 0.24$ days), intensifying by 2071–2100
 359 to -1 ± 0.21 days (RCP4.5) and -3.27 ± 0.38 days (RCP8.5). Negative values denote earlier first flights.
 360 Ensemble spread is limited, suggesting robust scenario-dependent advances. In practice, these changes
 361 are modest compared with *L. botrana*, but they may still warrant slightly earlier monitoring, especially
 362 in southern/eastern growing areas under RCP8.5.

363 (a)

364
365 (b)

366
367 (c)

368
369 *Figure 8. First occurrence of the first flight of E. ambiguella (ensemble mean). Top row: day of year (DOY) for 2003–*
370 *2022, 2021–2050, and 2071–2100. Bottom row: changes relative to 2003–2022 (days) for 2021–2050 and 2071–*
371 *2100. Results are shown for (a) RCP4.5 and (b) RCP8.5. The maps are restricted to areas suitable for viticulture,*

372 defined as Huglin Index ≥ 1500 . (c) Boxplots of changes in first-flight timing (ΔEA , days) within areas with HI \geq
 373 1500; the horizontal line marks no change (0).

374
 375 Looking at the individual locations and climate change projections, the changes up to 2035 are small
 376 with a range of +1 to -1. Higher values can be found only sporadically, with MPI-ESM-LR-CCLM4 RCP4.5
 377 also showing values of +3 days in the south. In RCP8.5, on the other hand, CM5A-MR_IPSL-INERIS-WRF
 378 shows an early shift of 4 days.

379 For 2085, the RCP4.5 are like those for 2035 and are in a range from 0 to -3. Due to the higher
 380 temperatures in RCP8.5, the occurrence occurs up to -7 days earlier, whereby the two projections
 381 CNRM-CM5_CNRM-ALADIN53 and CM5A-MR_IPSL-INERIS-WRF have the greatest shifts (Table 6).

382
 383 Table 6. Differences in the first occurrence of the 1st flight *E. ambiguella* between 2035 (2021-2050) and now
 384 (2003-2022) as well as 2085 (2071-2100) and now (2003-2022) - in days.

		CNRM-CM5_CLMcom-CCLM4	CNRM-CM5_CNRM-ALADIN53	EC-EARTH_DMI-HIRHAM5	CM5A-MR_IPSL-INERIS-WRF	MPI-ESM-LR-CCLM4	CNRM-CM5_CLMcom-CCLM4	CNRM-CM5_CNRM-ALADIN53	EC-EARTH_DMI-HIRHAM5	CM5A-MR_IPSL-INERIS-WRF	MPI-ESM-LR-CCLM4
RCP4.5											
Location	Climate and growth zones	2035					2085				
Seckau	Eastern Intermediate Alps - southern part	1	0	-1	0	1	-2	-1	-1	-1	0
Gumpoldskirchen	Lower Austrian eastern fringe of the Alps	1	1	-1	1	1	-1	-2	0	-1	0
Enns	Northern Alpine Foreland - Eastern part	1	1	0	1	1	-1	-2	0	-1	0
Gumpenstein		1	0	0	1	1	-2	-1	1	-2	0
Hoersching		1	1	0	1	1	-1	-2	0	-1	0
Melk		1	1	-1	1	1	-1	-1	0	-1	0
Rum	Northern Intermediate Alps - Western part	0	0	0	0	1	-1	-2	1	-3	-1
Ahrenberg	Pannonian lowlands and hills	1	1	-1	1	1	-1	-1	0	-1	0
Andau		0	0	-1	1	2	-2	-2	0	-1	0
Berg		1	0	-1	0	1	-1	-2	0	-1	0
Langenlois		1	1	-1	1	1	-1	-2	-1	-1	0
Lutzmannsburg		1	0	-1	1	2	-2	-2	0	-1	0
Rutzendorf		0	1	-1	1	1	-2	-2	0	-1	0
Schoengrabern		1	1	-1	1	1	-1	-2	-1	-1	0
Stammersdorf		1	1	-1	1	1	-1	-2	0	-1	0
Zwerndorf		0	0	-1	0	1	-2	-2	0	-1	0
Oberwoelz	Subcontinental Inner Alps - Eastern part	0	0	-1	1	1	-2	-1	-1	-1	0
Ratsch		0	0	0	2	3	-2	-1	0	1	0
Wagna Leibnitz	Sub-Illyrian hills and terraces	0	0	-1	2	3	-1	-2	0	1	0
Gmuend	Waldviertel region	-1	-1	-1	0	2	-3	-2	0	-1	0
Horn		1	0	-1	1	1	-1	-2	-1	-1	0
RCP8.5											
Seckau	Eastern Intermediate Alps - southern part	-1	-1	0	-2	0	-3	-4	-3	-5	-4
Gumpoldskirchen	Lower Austrian eastern fringe of the Alps	0	-1	1	-1	-1	-2	-4	-3	-5	-4
Enns	Northern Alpine Foreland - Eastern part	1	-2	0	0	0	-2	-5	-3	-4	-3
Gumpenstein		-1	-2	1	0	0	-4	-4	-3	-6	-4
Hoersching		1	-2	0	0	0	-2	-5	-3	-4	-3
Melk		0	-2	0	-1	0	-2	-5	-3	-5	-3

Rum	Northern Intermediate Alps - Western part	-1	-2	1	0	0	-5	-4	-3	-6	-5
Ahrenberg	Pannonian lowlands and hills	0	-2	0	-1	-1	-2	-4	-3	-5	-4
Andau		0	-1	0	-1	0	-2	-4	-2	-4	-3
Berg		0	-1	0	-1	-1	-2	-4	-3	-4	-3
Langenlois		0	-2	0	-1	0	-2	-5	-3	-5	-3
Lutzmannsburg		-1	-1	0	-1	-1	-2	-4	-3	-4	-3
Rutzendorf		0	-2	0	-1	-1	-2	-4	-3	-5	-3
Schoengrabern		0	-2	0	-1	0	-2	-5	-3	-4	-3
Stammersdorf		0	-1	0	-1	0	-2	-4	-3	-5	-3
Zwerndorf		0	-1	0	-1	-1	-2	-4	-3	-4	-3
Oberwoelz		Subcontinental Inner Alps - Eastern part	-1	-1	0	-1	-1	-4	-4	-3	-6
Ratsch	-1		-2	1	-4	-2	-2	-4	-2	-7	-4
Wagna Leibnitz	Sub-Illyrian hills and terraces	-1	-2	0	-4	-2	-2	-5	-2	-6	-4
Gmuend		Waldviertel region	-2	-1	0	-2	-1	-5	-4	-4	-5
Horn	0		-2	0	-1	0	-2	-5	-3	-5	-3

385

386 The first occurrence of the 2nd flight in 2035 in Langenlois, Lutzmannsburg, Retz, Stammersdorf, and
 387 Zwettl show an earlier occurrence of 1 (RCP4.5) and 2 (RCP8.5) day (ensemble mean). At the end of the
 388 century, clear differences between RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 can be recognised, reaching values of -2 and -4
 389 respectively (Figure 9). Here, too, Zwettl shows the smallest shift.

390

391

392 *Figure 9. Deviations in the first day of occurrence of Eupoecilia ambiguella 2nd flight in Langenlois,*
 393 *Lutzmannsburg, Retz, Stammersdorf, and Zwettl between 2021-2050 vs 2003-2022 and 2075-2100 vs 2003-2022:*
 394 *ensemble mean (black dashed lines) and selected ÖKS15 projections differences (bars).*

395

396 3.2.4 Climate change effect on American grapevine leafhopper (*S. titanus*)

397 The two observed nymphal stages of *S. titanus* (Figure 10) show different degrees of response under
 398 climate warming towards earlier first occurrence dates (up to -13 days) and that goes partly in parallel
 399 with shifted growing areas of the host plants. While the shifts towards earlier first occurrence dates of

400 N1 are still small (0 to -2 days), in the period 2021-2050, they increase up to 13 days earlier than now
 401 by the end of the century (RCP8.5). In N3, a shift of up to 5 days (RCP4.5) and up to 9 days (RCP8.5) is
 402 expected at the end of the century and is therefore not as pronounced as in N1 (Figure 10). Within
 403 viticulture-suitable areas ($HI \geq 1500$), mean changes confirm this pattern: for N1, $\Delta N1$ averages -9.5
 404 days under RCP8.5 by 2071-2100 (range -13.3 to -7.8) versus -5.3 days under RCP4.5 (-6.4 to -4.7).
 405 Near-term shifts are already larger under RCP8.5 (-1.7 days; -2.7 to -1.1) than under RCP4.5 (-1.3
 406 days; -2.3 to -0.7). For N3, end-century advances are smaller than for N1: -5.95 days under RCP8.5
 407 (-11.3 to -4.5) versus -3.93 days under RCP4.5 (-6.1 to -3.0). Across N1 and N3, RCP8.5 produces
 408 stronger mean advances and broader ranges; low standard deviations ($SD < 1$ day) indicate spatially
 409 homogeneous shifts rather than localized hotspots. Negative values ($\Delta N1$, $\Delta N3$) denote earlier first
 410 occurrences relative to 2003-2022.

416

417

418

419 *Figure 10. First occurrence (hatching) of *S. titanus* nymphal stages: (a) N1, (b) N3. Left panels: baseline 2003–*
 420 *2022 shown as day of year (DOY). Middle and right panels: changes relative to 2003–2022 (days) for 2021–2050*
 421 *and 2071–2100 under RCP4.5 (top row) and RCP8.5 (bottom row); negative values indicate earlier occurrence.*
 422 *Maps are restricted to viticulture-suitable areas (Huglin Index ≥ 1500). Bottom: boxplots of changes in timing ($\Delta N1$,*
 423 *$\Delta N3$; days) for the same periods and scenarios; the dashed line marks no change (0).*

424

425 The strongest impact can be expected in the EC-EARTH_DMI-HIRHAM5 projection for 2035. A shift of
 426 up to -4 days has been calculated for both emission scenarios. In CNRM-CM5_CLMcom-CCLM4 and
 427 CNRM-CM5_CNRM-ALADIN53, the expected effects are significantly higher in RCP8.5 than in RCP4.5,
 428 while the projection MPI-ESM-LR-CCLM4 shows exactly the opposite. At the end of the century, the
 429 differences between RCP4.5 simulations and RCP8.5 become significantly larger, reaching an advance
 430 shift from -5 days in RCP4.5 to over -10 days in RCP8.5 (Table 7).

431

432 *Table 7. Differences in the first hatching of N1 of *S. titanus* between 2035 (2021-2050) and now (2003-2022) as*
 433 *well as 2085 (2071-2100) and now (2003-2022) - in days.*

		CNRM-CM5_CLMcom-CCLM4	CNRM-CM5_CNRM-ALADIN53	EC-EARTH_DMI-HIRHAM5	CM5A-MR_IPSL-INERIS-WRF	MPI-ESM-LR-CCLM4	CNRM-CM5_CLMcom-CCLM4	CNRM-CM5_CNRM-ALADIN53	EC-EARTH_DMI-HIRHAM5	CM5A-MR_IPSL-INERIS-WRF	MPI-ESM-LR-CCLM4
RCP4.5											
Location	Climate and growth zones	2035					2085				
Seckau	Eastern Intermediate Alps - southern part	1	-1	-3	-3	-2	-4	-5	-5	-7	-6
Gumpoldskirchen	Lower Austrian eastern fringe of the Alps	2	0	-4	-2	-2	-4	-6	-5	-6	-6
Enns	Northern Alpine Foreland - Eastern part	2	0	-3	-3	-2	-4	-5	-5	-6	-6
Gumpenstein		1	0	-3	-3	-3	-5	-5	-5	-7	-6
Hoersching		1	1	-3	-3	-2	-4	-5	-5	-6	-6
Melk		1	1	-3	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-6	-6
Rum	Northern Intermediate Alps - Western part	0	0	-3	-3	-2	-5	-5	-4	-7	-7
Ahrenberg	Pannonian lowlands and hills	2	1	-3	-2	-3	-4	-5	-5	-6	-7
Andau		2	-1	-4	-2	-2	-4	-7	-5	-5	-6
Berg		2	0	-4	-2	-2	-4	-7	-5	-5	-6
Langenlois		1	1	-3	-2	-3	-4	-5	-5	-5	-7
Lutzmannsburg		2	0	-4	-1	-3	-4	-6	-6	-5	-6
Rutzendorf		2	0	-4	-2	-3	-4	-6	-5	-5	-6
Schoengrabern		1	1	-3	-2	-2	-4	-5	-5	-5	-7
Stammersdorf		2	0	-3	-2	-3	-4	-6	-5	-5	-7
Zwerndorf		1	0	-3	-2	-3	-4	-6	-5	-5	-6
Oberwoelz	Subcontinental Inner Alps - Eastern part	1	-1	-4	-2	-3	-5	-6	-5	-7	-7
Ratsch		2	0	-3	-2	-3	-4	-6	-5	-6	-6
Wagna Leibnitz	Sub-Illyrian hills and terraces	2	0	-4	-2	-3	-4	-5	-5	-6	-7
Gmuend	Waldviertel region	1	-1	-3	-2	-3	-5	-5	-5	-7	-7
Horn		1	0	-3	-2	-3	-3	-5	-5	-5	-7
RCP8.5											
Seckau	Eastern Intermediate Alps - southern part	-3	-4	-2	0	-1	-11	-12	-9	-11	-10
Gumpoldskirchen	Lower Austrian eastern fringe of the Alps	-3	-3	-4	1	-2	-9	-12	-10	-7	-9
Enns	Northern Alpine Foreland - Eastern part	-3	-3	-4	2	-1	-10	-12	-10	-6	-8
Gumpenstein		-4	-3	-3	1	-1	-13	-11	-11	-11	-12
Hoersching		-3	-3	-4	1	-1	-10	-12	-10	-6	-8
Melk		-3	-3	-4	2	-1	-9	-12	-10	-6	-8
Rum	Northern Intermediate Alps - Western part	-4	-2	-2	0	-2	-15	-11	-10	-12	-14
Ahrenberg	Pannonian lowlands and hills	-3	-3	-4	2	-2	-9	-12	-10	-6	-9
Andau		-3	-3	-4	1	-1	-9	-13	-10	-7	-8
Berg		-3	-3	-4	1	-1	-9	-13	-10	-6	-8
Langenlois		-2	-3	-4	2	-2	-9	-11	-9	-6	-9
Lutzmannsburg		-3	-4	-4	1	-2	-9	-13	-10	-7	-9
Rutzendorf		-3	-3	-4	2	-1	-9	-12	-10	-7	-9
Schoengrabern		-2	-3	-4	2	-2	-9	-12	-9	-5	-8
Stammersdorf		-3	-4	-4	2	-2	-9	-13	-10	-7	-9
Zwerndorf		-3	-3	-4	2	-2	-9	-12	-10	-6	-9
Oberwoelz	Subcontinental Inner Alps - Eastern part	-4	-4	-2	1	-2	-13	-12	-9	-11	-11
Ratsch		-2	-3	-3	0	-2	-10	-13	-10	-8	-10
Wagna Leibnitz	Sub-Illyrian hills and terraces	-3	-3	-3	0	-2	-10	-12	-10	-9	-10
Gmuend	Waldviertel region	-4	-3	-2	1	-2	-15	-11	-9	-12	-12
Horn		-2	-2	-4	2	-2	-8	-11	-9	-5	-8

434

435 As Figure 9 already shows, the N3 shifts are smaller overall than for N1. In 2035, the various projections
436 reach a range of 0 to -4 and the two emission scenarios do not differ greatly. For 2085, RCP8.5 shows
437 higher effects and reaches values of up to -13 days (Table 8). Clearly regional differences are not
438 discernible.

439

440 Table 8. Differences in the first hatching of N3 of *S. titanus* between 2035 (2021-2050) and now (2003-2022) as
 441 well as 2085 (2071-2100) and now (2003-2022) - in days.

		CNRM-CM5_CLMcom-CCLM4	CNRM-CM5_CNRM-ALADIN53	EC-EARTH_DMI-HIRHAM5	CM5A-MR_IPSL-INERIS-WRF	MPI-ESM-LR-CCLM4	CNRM-CM5_CLMcom-CCLM4	CNRM-CM5_CNRM-ALADIN53	EC-EARTH_DMI-HIRHAM5	CM5A-MR_IPSL-INERIS-WRF	MPI-ESM-LR-CCLM4
RCP4.5											
Location	Climate and growth zones	2035					2085				
Seckau	Eastern Intermediate Alps - southern part	-1	0	-4	-2	-2	-4	-7	-4	-3	-4
Gumpoldskirchen	Lower Austrian eastern fringe of the Alps	-2	-1	-4	-1	-2	-4	-5	-3	-3	-4
Enns	Northern Alpine Foreland - Eastern part	-1	-1	-3	-1	-2	-4	-5	-3	-3	-4
Gumpenstein		0	0	-4	-2	-2	-4	-7	-3	-5	-4
Hoersching		-1	-1	-3	-1	-2	-4	-5	-3	-3	-4
Melk		-2	-1	-3	-1	-2	-4	-5	-3	-3	-3
Rum	Northern Intermediate Alps - Western part	-2	-2	-3	-3	-3	-6	-7	-3	-5	-4
Ahrenberg	Pannonian lowlands and hills	-1	-1	-3	-1	-2	-4	-5	-3	-3	-3
Andau		-1	-1	-4	-1	-2	-4	-6	-4	-3	-4
Berg		-2	-2	-4	-1	-2	-4	-6	-4	-3	-4
Langenlois		-2	-1	-3	-1	-2	-4	-6	-3	-2	-3
Lutzmannsburg		-2	0	-3	-1	-2	-5	-5	-4	-3	-4
Rutzendorf		-1	-1	-3	-1	-2	-4	-6	-3	-3	-4
Schoengrabern		-2	-1	-3	-1	-2	-4	-5	-4	-3	-4
Stammersdorf		-2	-1	-4	-1	-2	-4	-5	-3	-3	-4
Zwerndorf		-2	-1	-3	-1	-2	-4	-6	-3	-3	-4
Oberwoelz	Subcontinental Inner Alps - Eastern part	-1	-1	-4	-1	-2	-4	-8	-4	-3	-4
Ratsch		-2	1	-3	-2	-2	-5	-4	-3	-3	-4
Wagna Leibnitz	Sub-Illyrian hills and terraces	-1	0	-3	-2	-2	-5	-4	-3	-3	-4
Gmuend	Waldviertel region	-1	-1	-4	-2	-3	-5	-7	-4	-4	-4
Horn		-2	-1	-3	0	-2	-4	-5	-3	-2	-4
RCP8.5											
Seckau	Eastern Intermediate Alps - southern part	-1	-2	-2	2	-2	-6	-11	-8	-3	-6
Gumpoldskirchen	Lower Austrian eastern fringe of the Alps	-2	0	-2	3	-1	-6	-7	-7	-2	-4
Enns	Northern Alpine Foreland - Eastern part	-1	0	-2	2	-2	-7	-8	-8	-3	-5
Gumpenstein		-1	-2	-2	1	-2	-7	-12	-8	-6	-5
Hoersching		-1	0	-2	2	-2	-7	-8	-7	-3	-5
Melk		-1	0	-2	3	-1	-6	-8	-7	-2	-5
Rum	Northern Intermediate Alps - Western part	-3	-2	-2	1	-2	-9	-13	-9	-6	-6
Ahrenberg	Pannonian lowlands and hills	-1	0	-2	3	-1	-6	-7	-7	-2	-4
Andau		-2	-1	-2	2	0	-7	-8	-7	-3	-3
Berg		-2	-1	-2	2	0	-7	-8	-7	-3	-3
Langenlois		-1	0	-2	3	0	-6	-7	-7	-2	-3
Lutzmannsburg		-1	-1	-2	2	-1	-7	-7	-7	-3	-4
Rutzendorf		-2	0	-2	3	-1	-7	-7	-7	-3	-4
Schoengrabern		-2	0	-3	3	0	-6	-7	-7	-2	-3
Stammersdorf		-2	0	-2	3	-1	-6	-7	-7	-1	-4
Zwerndorf		-2	0	-3	3	0	-6	-7	-7	-2	-4
Oberwoelz	Subcontinental Inner Alps - Eastern part	-2	-4	-3	2	-2	-7	-13	-10	-5	-6
Ratsch		-1	0	-1	3	-1	-6	-7	-7	-2	-5
Wagna Leibnitz	Sub-Illyrian hills and terraces	-1	0	-2	3	-1	-7	-8	-7	-2	-5
Gmuend	Waldviertel region	-3	-3	-2	2	-2	-9	-13	-9	-6	-6
Horn		-1	0	-3	3	0	-6	-7	-7	-2	-3

442

443 **4. Discussion**

444 Considering the first objective, new prediction models focusing on *L. botrana* and *E. ambiguella*
 445 (1st/2nd flight) and *S. titanus* (N1 / N3) were developed in this study. For the three selected vineyard

446 pests a large amount of monitoring data were available. After a quality check (e. g., transitions between
447 developmental stages are clearly recognisable, a 0-catch observation took place before the initial first
448 catch with pheromone traps, a reasonable low amount was observed during the initial occurrence),
449 only monitoring data of suitable quality were used for the development of the prediction models. The
450 prediction models were generated using multiple linear regression (MLR) analysis, which allows the
451 inclusion of several variables. In a preceding study by Blümel et al. (2020), the inclusion of different
452 weather variables was found to improve the prediction accuracy of mathematical forecasting models.
453 In this study, the developed models consisted of two to three weather variables. Model
454 calibration/validation indicated good correspondence with observations and low multicollinearity of
455 predictors (for the grape moths see Kolkmann et al., 2025b). For *S. titanus* existing predictions models
456 were further improved. Compared to the previous MLR models for *S. titanus* described in Kolkmann et
457 al. (2025a), the adapted MLR models reduced the average absolute deviations (2013-2022) by 0.66
458 days for N1 and by 1.43 days for N3. The six calibrated and validated multiple linear regression models,
459 which apply different processed weather parameters (based on temperature, precipitation, and -for
460 *E. ambiguella* 2nd flight- also global radiation), were integrated in ARIS to enable spatially consistent
461 daily simulations at 1 km resolution across Austria.

462 According to the assessment of future spatial shifts in suitable wine-growing areas and grapevine pest
463 occurrences (Objective 2) rising temperatures are expected to significantly reshape Austria's wine-
464 growing regions, making previously unsuitable areas viable for viticulture. The application of the Huglin
465 Index in this study provided an assessment of the impacts of climate change on viticultural suitability
466 across Austria. As a temperature-based metric, the Huglin Index provides valuable insights into how
467 warming trends are likely to shift suitable grape-growing zones northward and to higher elevations. In
468 our maps, potential wine regions are defined by a threshold of HI > 1500. The area above this threshold
469 increases from 2035 to 2085, most strongly under RCP8.5, with expansion focused on the northeast,
470 east and southeast, and along Alpine valleys at lower elevations. These findings align with broader
471 climate modelling studies, which predict an expansion of viticultural areas not only in Austria
472 (Prettenthaler et al. 2013) but also in other parts of Europe, such as Germany and Southern England
473 (Schultz 2016; Hannah et al. 2013). For example, Schultz (2016) highlights that rising temperatures are
474 already enabling viticulture in regions previously considered too cold, such as Southern England, while
475 Hannah et al. (2013) project significant shifts in grape-growing zones globally, driven by temperature
476 increases and changing precipitation patterns. These changes are already evident, as new vineyards
477 are being established in regions historically considered unsuitable for grape cultivation (Droulia and
478 Charalampopoulos 2021, 2022). Note that Austrian ensemble means indicate modest near-term
479 temperature increases but substantially larger late-century warming, especially under RCP8.5, while

480 precipitation responses show high inter-model spread; however, near-term warming is likely
481 underestimated in the ÖKS15 scenarios, implying that our near-term projections are conservative.
482 According to Objective 3 our results suggests that climate change will significantly alter the phenology
483 and geographic distribution of major grapevine pests, such as *L. botrana*, *E. ambiguella*, and *S. titanus*.
484 The development and behaviour of these pests are strongly influenced by environmental factors, with
485 temperature playing a particularly critical role in their growth and life cycles (Briere et al. 1999). Rising
486 temperatures, combined with altered precipitation patterns, are projected to create both challenges
487 and opportunities for pest management in viticulture. Reflecting the findings of Briere et al. (1999), the
488 pest prediction algorithms in this study prioritized temperature as the dominant variable, while also
489 accounting for precipitation to capture additional environmental influences. Our algorithms explicitly
490 use temperature as the primary driver and include precipitation (and global radiation for *E. ambiguella*
491 2nd flight) to capture additional environmental influences.

492 The results of this study show that the first occurrence of *L. botrana* is observed in eastern Austria in
493 late April (DOY 118) and along the Danube into Upper Austria by mid-May (DOY 130+). Under projected
494 climate change, it is expected that the timing will be brought forward to an earlier date. By 2035, shifts
495 to an earlier date are modest (\approx -1 day under RCP4.5; -1 to -2 days under RCP8.5). By 2085, advances
496 reach up to -5 days under RCP4.5 and up to -12 days under RCP8.5 (ensemble mean), with minimal
497 regional differences across the ensemble. These findings are consistent with Caffarra et al. (2012), who
498 projected earlier seasonal activity and more generations per year under warming scenarios. The
499 stronger shifts under RCP8.5 are consistent with a greater late-century warming signal over Austria. For
500 the second flight, we estimate a further 11-day advance under RCP8.5 by the end of the century. With
501 shifts to an earlier date of up to 23 days, a third generation is likely to occur regularly.

502 For *E. ambiguella*, the shifts are less pronounced. In 2035, changes are minimal (largely 0 to -1 day),
503 and by 2085 shifts reach up to -3 days (RCP4.5) and up to -5 days (RCP8.5; ensemble mean). These
504 smaller shifts align with the findings of Thiéry and Moreau (2005), who noted that *E. ambiguella* is less
505 sensitive to temperature changes compared to *L. botrana*. Thiéry et al. (2018) further suggest that
506 *E. ambiguella* may persist or even expand in cooler, wetter regions, which could explain the relatively
507 modest phenological shifts observed in this study. Our ensemble results show modest shifts to an
508 earlier date with limited regional differences, with slightly larger shifts under RCP8.5.

509 The two observed nymphal stages of *S. titanus* (N1 and N3) show varying degrees of response to climate
510 warming. For N1, shifts towards earlier first occurrence dates are relatively small in the near future (0
511 to -2 days) but increase up to 14 days earlier by the end of the century under RCP8.5. Given the likely
512 underestimation of near-term warming in the ÖKS15 scenarios, these near-future shifts represent
513 lower-bound estimates. For N3, the shifts are less pronounced, with up to 5 days earlier under RCP4.5

514 and up to 10 days earlier under RCP8.5 by the end of the century (ensemble mean). These results are
515 consistent with Sneiders et al. (2019), who projected similar changes in *S. titanus* phenology under
516 high-emission scenarios. However, Sneiders et al. (2019) also highlight that extreme heat in southern
517 regions could reduce female fertility, potentially limiting the expansion of *S. titanus* in these areas. This
518 raises the question of whether the shifts observed in Austria will differ in regions experiencing more
519 extreme heat. From a management perspective, earlier N1 occurrence implies moving up monitoring,
520 while N3 occurrence -used as a marker for timing insecticide applications- also shifts earlier and should
521 be reflected in warning systems, which provide guidance on the optimal timing of control measures.
522 This study provides a comprehensive assessment of the impacts of climate change on viticulture and
523 pest dynamics in Austria. Key strengths include the national-scale perspective, the integration of
524 calibrated pest algorithms into ARIS, and the use of a multi-member ÖKS15 ensemble with within-
525 model anomalies against 2003–2022 to isolate climate-change signals. Uncertainties are consistently
526 communicated via ensemble means and inter-member ranges, with precipitation changes showing
527 particularly high spread. However, some limitations remain. Pest prediction models could be further
528 improved by including additional ecological factors, such as host plant availability and variety, and
529 biological characteristics of the pests (Ainseba et al. 2011; Rigamonti et al. 2011; Thiéry et al. 2014;
530 Gilioli et al. 2016). In addition, prospective validation across more regions/years and comparison with
531 alternative phenology approaches would further strengthen operational guidance under both RCP4.5
532 and RCP8.5. A further limitation concerns the climate forcing: Austrian ÖKS15 projections likely
533 underestimate near-term warming relative to observations since the 1980s, reflecting both an
534 underestimation of greenhouse gas impacts and the masking effect of historical aerosol pollution. As
535 a result, our near-term signals should be viewed as lower-bound estimates, and RCP8.5 may be more
536 conservative than previously intended for near- to mid-term warming impacts. Updated scenarios
537 (ÖKS26) expected by late 2026/early 2027 should help refine these assessments.

538

539 **5. Conclusion**

540 This national assessment demonstrates climate-driven shifts in viticultural suitability and pest
541 phenology across Austria, using calibrated pest models integrated into ARIS and evaluated as within-
542 model anomalies relative to 2003–2022 from the ÖKS15 multi-member ensemble, with uncertainties
543 communicated via ensemble means and inter-member ranges. The framework operates daily on a 1
544 km grid, enabling spatially consistent decision support for Austrian wine regions. Increasing
545 temperatures in the growing-season heat, expanding areas above a Huglin Index (HI) threshold of 1500
546 and reinforcing the relevance of heat-resilient cultivars in existing eastern production zones, with the
547 strongest signals under late-century, high-emission scenarios. Pest activity shifts earlier across species,

548 implying earlier monitoring and intervention windows and favouring more targeted, seasonally
549 adjusted management. Robust warming signals contrast with large model spread in precipitation
550 responses, particularly by the late 21st century, underscoring the need for adaptive strategies and
551 iterative updates to decision frameworks. Further work will extend pest models to explicitly include
552 precipitation, solar radiation, and soil moisture, and to incorporate ecological determinants such as
553 host availability, grape variety, and species traits, complemented by broader prospective validation
554 and comparison with alternative phenology approaches. Overall, the study maps emerging suitability,
555 quantifies earlier pest activity at operational scales, and provides a foundation for earlier, dynamically
556 adjusted plant protection and climate-resilient planning in Austrian viticulture.

557

558 **Author contributions** All authors contributed to the conception and design of the study. S.T. prepared
559 the original draft and led the statistical analysis and visualisation; K.K. and S.B. calibrated and validated
560 the pest algorithms; F.L. provided and evaluated the ÖKS15 scenarios; V.D. implemented the ARIS
561 modelling; S.T. and J.E. reviewed and edited the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final
562 manuscript.

563

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569

570 **Data availability** The ÖKS15 projections are available from the GeoSphere Austria Data Hub
571 (<https://data.hub.geosphere.at/>)

572

573 **Declarations**

574 Competing interests The authors declare no competing interests.

575

576 **References**

- 577 Ainseba B, Picart D, Thiéry D (2011) An innovative multistage, physiologically structured, population
578 model to understand the European grapevine moth dynamics. *Journal of Mathematical*
579 *Analysis and Applications* 382 (1):34-46. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmaa.2011.04.021>
- 580 Altermatt F (2010) Climatic warming increases voltinism in European butterflies and moths. *Proc Biol*
581 *Sci* 277 (1685):1281-1287. doi:10.1098/rspb.2009.1910

582 Bauer K, Regner F, Friedrich B (2017) Weinbau. Cadmos Verlag GmbH, München, Germany

583 Blümel S, Eitzinger J, Gruber B, Gatterer M, Altenburger J, Hausdorf H (2020) Influence of weather
584 variables on the first seasonal occurrence of the grape berry moths *Eupoecilia ambiguella*
585 (Lepidoptera: Tortricidae) and *Lobesia botrana* (Lepidoptera: Tortricidae) in a case study region
586 in Austria. *Mitteilungen Klosterneuburg* 70 (2):115-128

587 Bradshaw CJ, Leroy B, Bellard C, Roiz D, Albert C, Fournier A, Barbet-Massin M, Salles JM, Simard F,
588 Courchamp F (2016) Massive yet grossly underestimated global costs of invasive insects. *Nat*
589 *Commun* 7 (1):12986. doi:10.1038/ncomms12986

590 Briere J-F, Pracros P, Le Roux A-Y, Pierre J-S (1999) A Novel Rate Model of Temperature-Dependent
591 Development for Arthropods. *Environmental Entomology* 28 (1):22-29.
592 doi:10.1093/ee/28.1.22

593 Caffarra A, Rinaldi M, Eccel E, Rossi V, Pertot I (2012) Modelling the impact of climate change on the
594 interaction between grapevine and its pests and pathogens: European grapevine moth and
595 powdery mildew. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 148:89-101.
596 doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2011.11.017

597 Castex V, Beniston M, Calanca P, Fleury D, Moreau J (2018) Pest management under climate change:
598 The importance of understanding tritrophic relations. *Science of The Total Environment* 616-
599 617:397-407. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.11.027

600 Castex V, García de Cortázar-Atauri I, Beniston M, Moreau J, Semenov M, Stoffel M, Calanca P (2023)
601 Exploring future changes in synchrony between grapevine (*Vitis vinifera*) and its major insect
602 pest, *Lobesia botrana*. *OENO One* 57 (1):161-174. doi:10.20870/oenone.2023.57.1.7250

603 Caudwell A (1990) Epidemiology and Characterization of Flavescence-Doree (Fd) and Other Grapevine
604 Yellows. *Agronomie* 10 (8):655-663. doi:DOI 10.1051/agro:19900806

605 Chimani B, Heinrich G, Hofstätter M, Kerschbaumer M, Kienberger S, Leuprecht A, Lexer A, Peßenteiner
606 S, Poetsch MS, Salzmann M, Spiekermann R, Switanek M, Truhetz H (2016) ÖKS15 –
607 Klimaszenarien für Österreich. Daten, Methoden und Klimaanalyse. Wien, Österreich

608 Chimani B, Matulla C, Eitzinger J, Hiebl J, Hofstätter M, Kubu G, Maraun D, Mendlik T, Schellander-
609 Gorgas T, Thaler S (2019) GUIDELINE zur Nutzung der ÖKS15-Klimawandelsimulationen,
610 Version 2. Wien, Austria

611 Chimani B, Matulla C, Hiebl J, Schellander-Gorgas T, Maraun D, Mendlik T, Eitzinger J, Kubu G, Thaler S
612 (2020) Compilation of a guideline providing comprehensive information on freely available
613 climate change data and facilitating their efficient retrieval. *Climate Services* 19:100179.
614 doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cliser.2020.100179

615 Clarke L, Edmonds J, Jacoby H, Pitcher H, Reilly J, Richels R (2007) Scenarios of Greenhouse Gas
616 Emissions and Atmospheric Concentrations.

617 Comte V, Schneider L, Sneiders B, Rebetez M (2024) Climate change is likely to favour polyvoltine and
618 invasive insect species, leading to more damage in the mid-latitude vineyards of Neuchatel
619 OENO One 58(4). doi:<https://doi.org/10.20870/oenone.2024.58.4.7767>

620 Droulia F, Charalampopoulos I (2021) Future Climate Change Impacts on European Viticulture: A Review
621 on Recent Scientific Advances. Atmosphere 12 (4):495

622 Droulia F, Charalampopoulos I (2022) A Review on the Observed Climate Change in Europe and Its
623 Impacts on Viticulture. Atmosphere 13 (5):837

624 EFSA (2014) Scientific Opinion on pest categorisation of Grapevine Flavescence dorée. EFSA Journal 12
625 (10):1-31. doi:[10.2903/j.efsa.2014.3851](https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2014.3851)

626 EFSA, Jeger M, Bragard C, Caffier D, Candresse T, Chatzivassiliou E, Dehnen-Schmutz K, Gilioli G, Jaques
627 Miret JA, MacLeod A, Navajas Navarro M, Niere B, Parnell S, Pottting R, Rafoss T, Rossi V, Urek
628 G, Van Bruggen A, Van Der Werf W, West J, Winter S, Bosco D, Foissac X, Strauss G, Hollo G,
629 Mosbach-Schulz O, Grégoire J-C (2016) Risk to plant health of Flavescence dorée for the EU
630 territory. EFSA Journal 14 (12):e04603. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2016.4603>

631 Eitzinger J, Daneu V, Kubu G, Thaler S, Trnka M, Schaumberger A, Schneider S, Tran TMA (2024) Grid
632 based monitoring and forecasting system of cropping conditions and risks by
633 agrometeorological indicators in Austria – Agricultural Risk Information System ARIS. Climate
634 Services 34:100478. doi:[10.1016/j.cliser.2024.100478](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cliser.2024.100478)

635 Falzoi S, Lessio F, Spanna F, Alma A (2014) Influence of temperature on the embryonic and post-
636 embryonic development of *Scaphoideus titanus* (Hemiptera: Cicadellidae), vector of grapevine
637 Flavescence dorée. International Journal of Pest Management 60 (4):246-257.
638 doi:[10.1080/09670874.2014.966170](https://doi.org/10.1080/09670874.2014.966170)

639 Fermaud M, Le Menn R (1989) Association of *Botrytis cinerea* with Grape Berry Moth Larvae.
640 Phytopathology 79 (6):651-656. doi:[10.1094/Phyto-79-651](https://doi.org/10.1094/Phyto-79-651)

641 Formayer H, Parajka J, Petermann JS (2025) Chapter 1. Physical and ecological manifestation of climate
642 change in Austria. Second Austrian Assessment Report on Climate Change | AAR2 - Full Report.
643 Verlag der Österreichischen Akademie der Wissenschaften, Wien

644 Fraga H, Malheiro AC, Moutinho-Pereira J, Santos JA (2012) An overview of climate change impacts on
645 European viticulture. Food and Energy Security 1 (2):94-110.
646 doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/fes3.14>

647 Gilioli G, Pasquali S, Marchesini E (2016) A modelling framework for pest population dynamics and
648 management: An application to the grape berry moth. *Ecological Modelling* 320:348-357.
649 doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2015.10.018>

650 Gonella E, Benelli G, Arricau-Bouvery N, Bosco D, Duso C, Dietrich CH, Galetto L, Rizzoli A, Jović J,
651 Mazzoni V, Mori N, Nieri R, Roversi PF, Strauss G, Thiéry D, Trivellone V, Virant-Doberlet M,
652 Lucchi A, Alma A (2024) *Scaphoideus titanus* forecasting and management: quo vadis?
653 *Entomologia Generalis* 44 (3):497-510. doi:10.1127/entomologia/2023/2598

654 Gutierrez A, Ponti L (2014) Analysis of invasive insects: links to climate change. CABI.
655 doi:10.1079/9781780641645.0045

656 Gutierrez AP, Ponti L, Gilioli G, Baumgärtner J (2018) Climate warming effects on grape and grapevine
657 moth (*Lobesia botrana*) in the Palearctic region. *Agricultural and Forest Entomology* 20 (2):255-
658 271. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/afe.12256>

659 Haiden T, Kann A, Pistotnik G (2012) Nowcasting with INCA During SNOW-V10. *Pure and Applied*
660 *Geophysics* 171 (1-2):231-242. doi:10.1007/s00024-012-0547-8

661 Haiden T, Kann A, Pistotnik G, Stadlbacher K, Wittmann C (2010) Integrated Nowcasting through
662 Comprehensive Analysis (INCA) System description. Central Institute for Meteorology and
663 Geodynamics.

664 Hannah L, Roehrdanz PR, Ikegami M, Shepard AV, Shaw MR, Tabor G, Zhi L, Marquet PA, Hijmans RJ
665 (2013) Climate change, wine, and conservation. *Proceedings of the National Academy of*
666 *Sciences* 110 (17):6907-6912. doi:doi:10.1073/pnas.1210127110

667 Hiebl J, Frei C (2016) Daily temperature grids for Austria since 1961—concept, creation and
668 applicability. *Theoretical and Applied Climatology* 124 (1):161-178. doi:10.1007/s00704-015-
669 1411-4

670 Höbaus E (1988) Distribution of the grape berry moth species *Eupoecilia ambiguella* Hb. and *Lobesia*
671 *botrana* Schiff. in Austria. *Pflanzenschutzberichte* 49(1): 34-40.

672 Hoppmann D, Holst H (1989) Biometeorologische Grundlagen für ein Prognosemodell des Einbindigen
673 und Bekreuzten Traubenwicklers. *Viticultura et Enologia Scientia (Vitic Enol Sci)* 44:132–140

674 Horel Á, Bakacsi Z, Vass C, Zsigmond T (2024) Inter-row soil management affecting soil moisture in non-
675 irrigated vineyard ecosystems: A meta-analysis. *Soil Use Manage* 40 (4).
676 doi:10.1111/sum.13159

677 Huglin P, Schneider C (1998) *Biologie et écologie de la vigne. Technique et documentation,*

678 Iltis C, Moreau J, Pecharová K, Thiéry D, Louâpre P (2020) Reproductive performance of the European
679 grapevine moth *Lobesia botrana* (Tortricidae) is adversely affected by warming scenario.
680 *Journal of Pest Science* 93 (2):679-689. doi:10.1007/s10340-020-01201-1

681 Jacob D, Petersen J, Eggert B, Alias A, Christensen OB, Bouwer LM, Braun A, Colette A, Déqué M,
682 Georgievski G, Georgopoulou E, Gobiet A, Menut L, Nikulin G, Haensler A, Hempelmann N,
683 Jones C, Keuler K, Kovats S, Kröner N, Kotlarski S, Kriegsmann A, Martin E, van Meijgaard E,
684 Moseley C, Pfeifer S, Preuschmann S, Radermacher C, Radtke K, Rechid D, Rounsevell M,
685 Samuelsson P, Somot S, Soussana J-F, Teichmann C, Valentini R, Vautard R, Weber B, Yiou P
686 (2014) EURO-CORDEX: new high-resolution climate change projections for European impact
687 research. *Reg Environ Change* 14 (2):563-578. doi:10.1007/s10113-013-0499-2

688 Jones GV, and Webb LB (2010) Climate Change, Viticulture, and Wine: Challenges and Opportunities.
689 *Journal of Wine Research* 21 (2-3):103-106. doi:10.1080/09571264.2010.530091

690 Kolkman K (2021) Development of a forecasting model to predict first hatching of American grapevine
691 leafhopper (*Scaphoideus titanus*) nymphal stages in selected locations in Austria [Master's
692 Thesis]. [Austria]: University of Natural Resources - BOKU.

693 Kolkman K, Strauss G, Eitzinger J, Blümel S (2025a) Forecasting model to predict the first occurrence
694 of *Scaphoideus titanus* nymphal stages in selected locations in Austria. *Journal of Central*
695 *European Agriculture* 26 (1):126-138. doi:10.5513/jcea01/26.1.4308

696 Kolkman K, Blümel S, Eitzinger J (2025b) Predicting the first seasonal occurrence of *Lobesia botrana*
697 and *Eupoecilia ambiguella* in Austria using new multiple linear regression models *Oeno One* 59
698 (3). doi:ARTN 826910.20870/oeno-one.2025.59.3.8269

699 Kovács E, Puskás J, Pozsgai A, Kozma K (2018) Shift in the annual growth cycle of grapevines (*Vitis*
700 *vinifera* L.) in West Hungary. *Applied Ecology and Environmental Research* 16 (2):2029-2042.
701 doi:10.15666/aeer/1602_20292042

702 Lastuvka Z (2009) Climate change and its possible influence on the occurrence and importance of insect
703 pests. *Plant Protection Science* 45:S53-S62. doi:10.17221/2829-PPS

704 Martín-Vertedor D, Ferrero-García JJ, Torres-Vila LM (2010) Global warming affects phenology and
705 voltinism of *Lobesia botrana* in Spain. *Agricultural and Forest Entomology* 12 (2):169-176.
706 doi:https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-9563.2009.00465.x

707 Micciché D, Puccio S, Di Lorenzo R, Turano L, Di Carlo F, Pisciotta A (2025) Adapting Viticulture to
708 Climate Change: Impact of Shading in Sicily. *Horticulturae* 11 (2).
709 doi:10.3390/horticulturae11020163

710 Morone C, Boveri M, Giosuè S, Gotta P, Rossi V, Scapin I, Marzachi C (2007) Epidemiology of Flavescence
711 Dorée in Vineyards in Northwestern Italy. *Phytopathology*® 97 (11):1422-1427.
712 doi:10.1094/phyto-97-11-1422

713 Moss RH, Edmonds JA, Hibbard KA, Manning MR, Rose SK, van Vuuren DP, Carter TR, Emori S, Kainuma
714 M, Kram T, Meehl GA, Mitchell JFB, Nakicenovic N, Riahi K, Smith SJ, Stouffer RJ, Thomson AM,
715 Weyant JP, Wilbanks TJ (2010) The next generation of scenarios for climate change research
716 and assessment. *Nature* 463 (7282):747-756. doi:10.1038/nature08823

717 O'Brien RM (2007) A caution regarding rules of thumb for variance inflation factors. *Quality and*
718 *Quantity* 41 (5):673-690. doi:10.1007/s11135-006-9018-6

719 Paini DR, Sheppard AW, Cook DC, De Barro PJ, Worner SP, Thomas MB (2016) Global threat to
720 agriculture from invasive species. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 113
721 (27):7575-7579. doi:doi:10.1073/pnas.1602205113

722 Pavan F, Floreani C, Barro P, Zandigiaco P, Dalla Montà L (2013) Occurrence of two different
723 development patterns in *Lobesia botrana* (Lepidoptera: Tortricidae) larvae during the second
724 generation. *Agricultural and Forest Entomology* 15 (4):398-406.
725 doi:https://doi.org/10.1111/afe.12027

726 Peßenteiner S, Hohmann C, Kirchengast G, Schöner W (2021) High-resolution climate datasets in
727 hydrological impact studies: Assessing their value in alpine and pre-alpine catchments in
728 southeastern Austria. *Journal of Hydrology: Regional Studies* 38:100962.
729 doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejrh.2021.100962

730 Polesny F, Rupf O, Kühner E (2000) Tortricid pests in orchards and viticulture, from basic data sampling
731 to Internet warning service. *EPPO Bulletin* 30:127-129. doi:10.1111/j.1365-
732 2338.2000.tb00864.x

733 Pretenthaler F, Formayer H, Bonnardot V, Políticas Zentrum für Wirtschafts- und I (2013) Weinbau und
734 Klimawandel : erste Analysen aus Österreich und führenden internationalen Weinbaugebieten.
735 Studien zum Klimawandel in Österreich 9:XIV, 300 S., Ill., zahlr. graph. Darst. und Kt., 327 cm

736 Reineke A, Thiéry D (2016) Grapevine insect pests and their natural enemies in the age of global
737 warming. *Journal of Pest Science* 89 (2):313-328. doi:10.1007/s10340-016-0761-8

738 Reis S, Martins J, Gonçalves F, Carlos C, Santos JA (2022) European Grapevine Moth and *Vitis vinifera* L.
739 Phenology in the Douro Region: (A)synchrony and Climate Scenarios. *Agronomy* 12 (1):98

740 Riahi K, Grübler A, Nakicenovic N (2007) Scenarios of long-term socio-economic and environmental
741 development under climate stabilization. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* 74
742 (7):887-935. doi:10.1016/j.techfore.2006.05.026

743 Ricciardi R, Benelli G, Di Giovanni F, Lucchi A (2024) The European grape berry moth, *Eupoecilia*
744 *ambiguella* (Lepidoptera: Tortricidae): Current knowledge and management challenges. *Crop*
745 *Prot* 180:106641. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cropro.2024.106641

746 Rigamonti IE, Jermini M, Fuog D, Baumgärtner J (2011) Towards an improved understanding of the
747 dynamics of vineyard-infesting *Scaphoideus titanus* leafhopper populations for better timing
748 of management activities. *Pest Manag Sci* 67 (10):1222-1229.
749 doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/ps.2171>

750 Santos JA, Fraga H, Malheiro AC, Moutinho-Pereira J, Dinis L-T, Correia C, Moriondo M, Leolini L, Dibari
751 C, Costafreda-Aumedes S, Kartschall T, Menz C, Molitor D, Junk J, Beyer M, Schultz HR (2020) A
752 Review of the Potential Climate Change Impacts and Adaptation Options for European
753 Viticulture. *Applied Sciences* 10 (9):3092

754 Schultz HR (2016) Global Climate Change, Sustainability, and Some Challenges for Grape and Wine
755 Production. *Journal of Wine Economics* 11 (1):181-200. doi:10.1017/jwe.2015.31

756 Schultz HR, Stoll M (2010) Some critical issues in environmental physiology of grapevines: future
757 challenges and current limitations. *Australian Journal of Grape and Wine Research* 16 (s1):4-
758 24. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1755-0238.2009.00074.x>

759 Skendžić S, Zovko M, Živković IP, Lešić V, Lemić D (2021) The Impact of Climate Change on Agricultural
760 Insect Pests. *Insects* 12 (5). doi:10.3390/insects12050440

761 Sneiders B, Fleury D, Goyette S, Jermini M Influence du réchauffement climatique sur la dynamique des
762 populations de "*Scaphoideus titanus*" en Romandie. In, 2019.

763 Svobodova E, Trnka M, Dubrovsky M, Semeradova D, Eitzinger J, Stepanek P, Zalud Z (2014)
764 Determination of areas with the most significant shift in persistence of pests in Europe under
765 climate change. *Pest Manag Sci* 70 (5):708-715. doi:10.1002/ps.3622

766 Switanek MB, Troch PA, Castro CL, Leuprecht A, Chang HI, Mukherjee R, Demaria EMC (2017) Scaled
767 distribution mapping: a bias correction method that preserves raw climate model projected
768 changes. *Hydrol Earth Syst Sc* 21 (6):2649-2666

769 Thiéry D, Louâpre P, Muneret L, Rusch A, Sentenac G, Vogelweith F, Iltis C, Moreau J (2018) Biological
770 protection against grape berry moths. A review. *Agron Sustain Dev* 38 (2):15.
771 doi:10.1007/s13593-018-0493-7

772 Thiéry D, Monceau K, Moreau J (2014) Different emergence phenology of European grapevine moth
773 (*Lobesia botrana*, Lepidoptera: Tortricidae) on six varieties of grapes. *Bulletin of Entomological*
774 *Research* 104 (3):277-287. doi:10.1017/S000748531300031X

775 Thiéry D, Moreau J (2005) Relative performance of European grapevine moth (*Lobesia botrana*) on
776 grapes and other hosts. *Oecologia* 143 (4):548-557. doi:10.1007/s00442-005-0022-7

777 Tilg AM, Chimani B (2025) Austrian Climate Development 1961-2020 based on climate normal periods.
778 *Meteorol Z* 34 (3):151-180. doi:10.1127/metz/1250

779 Tosato DR, VanVolkenburg H, Vasseur L (2023) An Overview of the Impacts of Climate Change on
780 Vineyard Ecosystems in Niagara, Canada. *Agriculture (Switzerland)* 13 (9).
781 doi:10.3390/agriculture13091809

782 van Leeuwen C, Darriet P (2016) The Impact of Climate Change on Viticulture and Wine Quality. *Journal*
783 *of Wine Economics* 11:150-167. doi:10.1017/jwe.2015.21

784 van Leeuwen C, Friant P, Choné X, Tregoat O, Koundouras S, Dubourdieu D (2004) Influence of Climate,
785 Soil, and Cultivar on Terroir. *American Journal of Enology and Viticulture* 55 (3):207-217.
786 doi:10.5344/ajev.2004.55.3.207

787 van Vuuren DP, Edmonds J, Kainuma M, Riahi K, Thomson A, Hibbard K, Hurtt GC, Kram T, Krey V,
788 Lamarque J-F, Masui T, Meinshausen M, Nakicenovic N, Smith SJ, Rose SK (2011) The
789 representative concentration pathways: an overview. *Climatic Change* 109 (1-2):5-31.
790 doi:10.1007/s10584-011-0148-z

791 Yan Y, Wang Y-C, Feng C-C, Wan P-HM, Chang KT-T (2017) Potential distributional changes of invasive
792 crop pest species associated with global climate change. *Applied Geography* 82:83-92.
793 doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apgeog.2017.03.011>